

“Autonomy and Measurable Development: A Difference-in-Differences Analysis of the Impact of the EZLN in Chiapas (2000–2020)”

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Abstract

In the current era, development has taken on an increasing role, along with more alternative economic models because the environmental and inequality problems make need to rethink the economic systems. This study presents an exploratory econometric analysis of the Zapatista movement's impact on local development in Chiapas, Mexico. Using a Difference-in-Differences (DiD) model applied to census data from 2000, 2010, and 2020, it compares two municipalities: Chilón (control) and Las Margaritas (treated) so the article explores EZLN. The findings were that the EZLN has not had an impact, but this finding has limitations, such as the model and the lack of data, which forces us to reconsider the creation of new metrics and improve the quantitative analysis of alternative economic models to evaluate alternative development models in the Global South.

1. Introduction

As economists, it is essential to stay abreast of the social, political, and economic dynamics shaping today's world, especially in an increasingly globalized context facing various problems such as inequality and lack of development. In this context, the study of alternative forms of self-governance and more inclusive models helps in the creation of development policies. In the case of Mexico, a watershed event in governance was the emergence of the EZLN at a time when neoliberalism seemed to be the definitive future of Mexico and indigenous peoples opted for their own model.

This movement emerged from the first Declaration of the Lacandon Jungle in 1994, criticizing resource exploitation (EZLN, Portal 1994 and 1995). For several authors, this uprising was not only a reaction to NAFTA, but also the result of years of Indigenous resistance and marginalization, a demand for autonomy (Harvery 1998, Collier and Quaratiello 2005). From this initial stage of confrontation, the movement evolved toward new forms of political articulation and communication, making the EZLN a global symbol of anti-liberalism, advocating for Indigenous rights in the face of globalization (Stephen 2002). This movement, however, has undergone various evolutions, from the strongest opposition to the Mexican government to adapting to expand its narrative through digital media (Olessen 2004) while simultaneously promoting a model based on solidarity and a community economy (Nash 2001). Despite the EZLN's prominence in studies on the movement, gaps in literature persist, primarily regarding quantitative analysis in the communities. Although Speed (2008) and Postero (2007) address autonomy, they do not analyze its quantitative impact on measurable development.

This research aims to empirically evaluate whether EZLN's presence is associated with improvements in human development indicators. The central hypothesis is that its presence has a positive effect on the quality of life, as observed through population censuses. The

unit of analysis is the municipalities of Chiapas, allowing us to determine whether measurable well-being has improved in Zapatista communities compared to non-Zapatista communities.

This approach allows for a systematic and rigorous evaluation of the effects of Zapatismo as a concrete experience of indigenous politics and a development alternative. The objectives of this paper are to compare human development indicators in municipalities with and without a Zapatista presence; and estimate the causal effect of the Zapatista model using the difference-in-differences (DiD) method.

2. Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

2.1 Development and Indigenous Autonomy

For a better understanding of this analysis, it is important to understand the concept of sustainable development, especially for Indigenous peoples, as this definition cannot be separated from their worldview (Martínez Luna, 2013). A balance between human beings and community life is key, as the strengthening of their systems through autonomy is sought (Toledo, 2006). Development is not measured by indicators such as GDP, but rather by criteria of well-being and environmental conservation (Gudynas, 2011).

Communities often value autonomy, which is why self-governance models are common. This is the ability of a community to govern itself according to its own rules without depending on other entities. This represents a decentralization of power that promotes citizen participation (Ostrom, 1990; Prats, 2005). It implies accountability and transparency in community policymaking (Smith, 2005). Poverty, understood from a multidimensional perspective, constitutes another key concept within this theoretical framework. Poverty cannot be defined solely as low income but as an inability to meet all needs for a dignified life (Sen, 1999). In Mexico, this poverty is measured by CONEVAL (National Commission for the Promotion of Social Welfare) using indicators such as income, access to education, healthcare, social security, and other basic services (CONEVAL, 2023). Defining poverty contributes to the multidimensional approach necessary for assessing development in this community context.

2.2 Customs and Traditions in Mexico and Latin America

In states like Oaxaca, the legalization of internal regulatory systems has allowed communities to exercise their right to self-government through customs and practices, particularly in electoral processes (Van Cott, 2000). Article 2 of the Constitution recognizes these rights of Indigenous communities to self-determination, guiding them to apply a regulatory system and conflict resolution that respects human rights and dignity, recognizing the term "customs and practices" within the Mexican legal framework. This system of customs and practices is not simply cultural traditions, but legitimate forms of exercising political and social power within Indigenous communities (CIESAS, 2016, p. 55). This recognition began in 1992 with the recognition of the country as a multicultural one, recognizing its diversity. However, it wasn't until 2001 that Article 2 was amended,

recognizing the right to self-determination of Indigenous peoples and the implementation of their policies (Muciño, 2008).

One contribution was the idea of an Indigenous community where community life is regulated by oral tradition and the Indigenous worldview (González Galván, 2002).

The EZLN has implemented its own systems adapted to the needs of Indigenous peoples, with reports of how they transformed their subsistence agriculture into a political practice through autonomy (Hernandez and Jaffee, 2022). Even so, various authors have pointed out that autonomy does not in itself guarantee measurable development or the improvement of social indicators. Yashar (2005) warns about the modern state's need to translate collective rights into performance metrics. Escobar (2010) points to the incompatibility between community visions and technocratic development models. At the operational level, Postero (2007) and Speed (2008) agree that Zapatista autonomy faces material, institutional, and social challenges, including accountability and administrative sustainability.

Similar self-management models have emerged in Bolivia. In Bolivia, the 2009 Constitution recognizes Indigenous Originary Peasant Autonomy (AIOC), a model of self-government that allows communities to organize according to their customs and practices. The emblematic case of Charagua Iyambae represents the first consolidated AIOC in the country, where an Indigenous form of government based on traditional structures, indigenous norms, and communal democracy has been established (Fabricant, 2013; Postero, 2017; Céspedes, 2018). These initiatives have sought to materialize the principles of plurinationality and decolonization of the Bolivian state, although they face structural and implementation challenges.

Unlike other studies focused on the symbolism or political discourse of the EZLN, this work emphasizes an empirical exploration of its impacts. One of the main limitations of existing literature is the limited empirical evaluation of the Zapatista model and the lack of data. For this reason, DiD will be used to study the community's impact, employing the difference-in-differences (DiD) method, which has been widely used to identify causal effects in observational studies (Angrist and Pischke, 2009). For example, Card and Krueger (1994) applied this approach to compare the effects of a minimum wage increase on employment in fast-food restaurants between New Jersey and Pennsylvania.

Given the above, this study seeks to evaluate and explore, using census data and the DiD method, whether municipalities with Zapatista presence present significant differences in quality of life compared to those without. While it is important to increase empirical studies, in the case of Zapatismo, most studies have focused on political analysis, neglecting to evaluate quantitative effects (Solano, 2013). Similarly, the limited comparison of the Zapatista model with other indigenous models. Similar self-management models have been highlighted in Bolivia. In Bolivia, the 2009 Constitution recognizes Indigenous Originary Peasant Autonomy (AIOC), a model of self-government that allows communities to organize according to their customs and practices. The emblematic case of Charagua Iyambae represents the first consolidated AIOC in the country, where a form of Indigenous governance based on traditional structures, indigenous norms, and communal democracy

has been established (Fabricant, 2013; Postero, 2017; Céspedes, 2018). These initiatives have sought to materialize the principles of pluractionality and decolonization of the Bolivian state, although they face structural and implementation challenges. However, despite constitutional recognition, practical and political limitations persist that restrict the full extent of this autonomy (González, 2010).

3. Methodology

3.1 Justification of the Methodological Approach

For the analysis, a longitudinal analysis will be used to compare two municipalities that had similar economic parameters in the early 1990s, except that one had Zapatista influence and the other did not. Using the parameters will allow us to better visualize how municipality has evolved over the years and what the impact was.

Below is a comparison between the municipalities of Chilón and Las Margaritas, both located in the state of Chiapas, Mexico, based on data from the 2000 Population and Housing Census. In this case, a difference-and-differences (D&D) analysis can be applied, as this is a comparison of municipalities.

Las Margaritas is characterized by being a municipality with a historical and active EZLN presence since 1994, while Chilón has no formal EZLN presence (it serves as a control group). After research, databases from 2000, 2010, and 2020 will be used, allowing for a comparison between time periods. The presence of the EZLN and its form of self-governance will be considered an institutional treatment. Municipalities were used as proxy units for the treatment, which represents a common approach in territorial studies with statistical limitations (Lechner, 2011). To assume parallel trends between the two municipalities, the Housing Census indicates that both are in the state of Chiapas, with similar climate, indigenous groups, and population. Chilón had 77,686 inhabitants in 2000, while Las Margaritas had 87,034, and similar illiteracy levels. Chilón had 15,343 illiterate people over the age of 15, while Las Margaritas had 15,321 (INEGI, 2002).

For this model, trajectories will begin in 2000 to identify greater differences and to ensure that no other federal programs or events impacted only one of the municipalities during that period. It is important to collect comparable data between the two years. Although it is important to emphasize that there are limitations due to the lack of exact data on the Zapatista caracoles, municipalities are used as proxy units for institutional analysis.

For this reason, the DID method, which has been dominant in economics, is ideal for this study, allowing it to analyze the effects of policies and interventions (Roth et al., 2023). It allows for the use of longitudinal data from two groups to estimate the causal effect (Columbia Health, n.d.).

3.2 Model Explanation

The DiD approach allows for comparing developmental evolution in two groups (treated and control) before and after a time cutoff point, controlling for common trends and

structural factors by comparing Las Margaritas, which has a Zapatista presence, to Chilón, which does not.

The DiD model estimates the average treatment effect by comparing temporal changes between groups, a common approach used in impact evaluations (Angrist & Pischke, 2009). The basic specification is as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Tratado}_i + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Post}_t + \beta_3 \cdot (\text{Tratado}_i \times \text{Post}_t) + \gamma X_{it} + \varepsilon$$

Y_{it} : Dependent variable – development of municipality or community i in year t

Tratado_i : Dummy equal to 1 for the treated municipality (Las Margaritas), 0 for the control (Chilon)

Post_t : Dummy temporal igual a 1 si $t \geq 2010$

$\text{Tratado}_i \times \text{Post}_t$: Interaction term, its coefficient β_3 is the estimated causal effect of the EZLN

X_{it} : Structured control variable vector

ε_{it} : Random error term

Hypothesis

- Null hypothesis (H_0): $\beta_3=0$

EZLN had no effect on development.

- Alternative hypothesis (H_1): $\beta_3 \neq 0$

EZLN did have an effect (positive or negative).

The estimation was performed using linear regression with heteroskedasticity-robust errors (White, 1980), which improves the precision of standard errors when there is non-constant variance.

3.3 Variables used

The dependent variable, referred to as 'development', is a composite index aggregating. The analysis covers the period 2000–2020, using the Censos de Población y Vivienda del INEGI from those years as the main source. The following were used as independent variables:

Variable	Definition	Level
niños_sinkinder	Children under 5 years of age who do not attend school	Municipal
Lang_ind	Population over 5 years of age who speak an indigenous language	Municipal
Pobt	Total population	Municipal
menor15_anf	Children under 15 years of age who cannot read or write	Municipal

Mayor15_anf	People over 15 years old who do not write or read	Municipal
Educ_primaria	People aged 15 to 130 who have completed at most 6 grades of primary school.	Municipal
Educ_secundaria	People aged 15 to 130 who have completed at most 3 grades of secondary school.	Municipal
Educ_superior	People aged 18 to 130 who have completed at most one of the following: high school or bachelor's degree; basic normal school; technical or commercial studies with a secondary school diploma; technical or commercial studies with a high school diploma; bachelor's or professional normal school; master's or doctorate degree.	Municipal
Pea	Economically active population	Municipal
Piso_material	Private inhabited homes with cement or solid floors, wood, mosaic or other material	Municipal
hab2_mas	Homes with more than 2 rooms	Municipal
Hab1	One-room apartments	Municipal
Electricity	Homes with electricity	Municipal
Wáter	Homes with piped water	Municipal
Drenaje	Homes with drainage systems	Municipal
No_goods	Homes that do not have goods such as a refrigerator, car, etc.	Municipal

Prepared using data from the 2000, 2010 and 2020 Housing Census

Six databases were created in Excel, and a panel was created in Stata to implement the econometric model. Each municipality had its own databases with variables from the years 2000, 2010, and 2020. The data were grouped by municipality and year. Because some variables, such as the internet, were only presented from 2010 onward, they were excluded, and there were also variables such as social programs that cannot be quantified.

3.4 Applied Model

Applying this model to the context of this study, with the specific variables used, the estimation is defined as follows:

$$\text{development}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{tratado}_i + \beta_2 \cdot \text{post}_t + \beta_3 \cdot (\text{tratado}_i \times \text{post}_t) + \gamma_1 \cdot \text{menor15_anf}_{it} + \gamma_2 \cdot \text{mayor15_anf}_{it} + \gamma_3 \cdot \text{hab1}_{it} + \gamma_4 \cdot \text{no_goods}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

The variable Y development is constructed from: educacion_primaria, educacion_secundaria, educ_superior, PEA, agua, luz, internet, piso_material, hab2_mas, sanitario.

In addition to the treatment variables

Variable Description

treated 1 = Las Margaritas (EZLN), 0 = Chilón

post 1 = Year 2010 or later, 0 = Year 2000

DiD Interaction: tratado \times post

And finally, the control variables

Variable Description

menor15_anf: number of illiterate people under 15 years of age

mayor15_anaf: number of illiterate people over 15 years of age

hab1: number of single-room households

no_goods: number of households without durable goods (TV, refrigerator, etc.)

3.5 Justification of variables

The dependent variable "development" was constructed as a composite index that groups together key dimensions of social and economic development at the municipal level. It includes educational variables (primary, secondary, and higher education), economic participation (PEA), access to basic services (water, electricity, internet, and sanitation), and material housing conditions (floor type and number of rooms). These dimensions reflect both structural well-being and access to basic rights and allow for a broader understanding of development than a single indicator. Regarding the control variables included in vector X_{it} , structural factors were chosen that could have differentially influenced the evolution of development across municipalities, regardless of the presence of the EZLN. The variable "menor15_anf" measures educational lag in children and adolescents, while "mayor15_anaf" captures the accumulated lag among adults, which impacts the intergenerational transmission of human capital. The variable "hab1" represents overcrowding, associated with multidimensional poverty, and "no_goods" captures extreme property poverty, indicating households without durable goods. These variables allow us to control for initial structural inequalities that could bias the estimation of the EZLN's effect.

The variable "tratado" identifies the municipality with an EZLN presence (Las Margaritas), while "post" indicates the period after 2010, which was chosen as the temporal cutoff point. The DiD interaction represents the differential effect of the EZLN on development, which is the key coefficient in the analysis.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 General Results

The estimation of the difference-in-differences (DiD) model with controls shows a coefficient for the DiD interaction of -12.08 , indicating that Las Margaritas experienced, on

average, 12 points less development than the comparison municipality (Chilón) after 2010. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.178$), so it cannot be confidently stated that the presence of the EZLN had a negative or positive effect on the measured development. Preliminarily, the EZLN's impact appears unobservable through the available INEGI data.

The model includes controls such as illiteracy among children under 15, adults over 15, overcrowding, and property poverty. Of all the variables, the only one statistically significant at the 1% level was `niños_sinkinder`, with a coefficient of 1.29 ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that development is positively associated with the presence of school-age children (although this could reflect population size or age structure).

4.2 Discussion

The model was estimated with 2,358 observations and reports an R^2 of 1.0000, which could indicate an overfitting problem. This outlier reinforces the need to interpret the results with caution and avoid assuming a deterministic relationship between the included variables.

This situation is because the development index was constructed from structural variables (education, health, housing) that also act as relevant controls in the model. Despite this overfitting, it was decided to maintain these variables in the specification so as not to disrupt the internal logic of the study's territorial and structural approach.

In summary, although the econometric model does not support a positive effect of the EZLN on municipal development based on the selected variables, these findings must be contextualized considering the limitations of the data, political changes in subsequent six-year terms, and the complexity of capturing processes of social transformation through quantitative approaches.

Table of parallel trends between Chilón and Las Margaritas between 2000 and 2010

Prepared using data from the 2000, 2010 and 2020 Housing Census

The blue line represents the development of Las Margaritas, while the red line represents Chilón.

This result contradicts the initial hypothesis that proposed a possible positive impact of the EZLN on local development levels. The graphic validation of the assumption of parallel trends, a central requirement for the rigorous application of the DiD model, shows that since 2000, the two municipalities have not evolved in parallel. While Chilón shows marked growth in the development index between 2000 and 2010, Las Margaritas maintains a stagnant trend. This limits the causal validity of the estimator and suggests that preexisting structural conditions between the two municipalities could have strongly influenced the results.

5. Limitations of the Study

Despite its methodological contributions, this analysis faces significant limitations. The main one is the availability and quality of the data: municipal censuses do not fully capture the internal dynamics of development or the specific actions of the EZLN. Furthermore, it was not possible to empirically verify the assumption of parallel trends prior to treatment, which limits the causal validity of the model. No data was included, including individual surveys or detailed administrative records on public investment, health, or education. Institutional variables such as state presence or internal Zapatista governance mechanisms were also not included. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as exploratory and inconclusive.

Furthermore, Chilón was found to have received specific federal support during the 2012–2018 six-year term, related to investment in infrastructure and social programs. This type of external intervention—not attributable to the EZLN—represents an uncontrolled variable that may have accelerated development in Chilón, thus generating a distortion in the comparison (Superior Audit Office of the Federation [ASF], 2020; Municipal Council of Chilón, 2024). In contrast, although Las Margaritas has also received social support from the federal government (Secretaría de Bienestar, 2023) and resources from the FISMDF (ASF, 2020), the magnitude and type of state intervention in each municipality has been unequal, which limits a direct comparison in terms of Zapatista impact.

Another factor to consider is the limited availability of disaggregated data, both at the community level and in continuous development indicators. This necessitated the construction of a composite index based on census variables, whose coverage and periodicity prevent the capture of finer-grained dynamics, such as those generated by community action or Zapatista autonomy. Added to this is the limited documentation on forced displacement or internal migration in recent years, which may also alter the observed patterns (Piedra de Página, 2019; Velasco Ortiz & Contreras Rodríguez, 2018; Chiapas Paralelo, 2020).

Despite these limitations, this study represents a pioneering contribution to the quantitative assessment of the EZLN's territorial impact. Most previous work on Zapatismo has been qualitative, historical, or testimonial (Beaucage, 2005; Rauch & Schachtel, 2019). Studies

such as Andrews (2013) and Ross (2019) have documented the crucial role of NGOs and ideology in legitimizing the Zapatista movement, while others have highlighted the complex web of alliances and ruptures with social and religious actors (review of ¡Todos somos zapatistas!, n.d.). This paper introduces a formal econometric methodology to address the question of whether the EZLN contributed to local development. Although the results do not confirm this hypothesis, the application of the DiD model opens an original and relevant research agenda, combining political economy, census data, and territorial analysis. It also explores whether other metrics may be more appropriate in Indigenous contexts.

6. Conclusions

This paper explored the impact of the EZLN on municipal development using a difference-in-differences (DiD) model between Chilón (without a Zapatista presence) and Las Margaritas (with a strong Zapatista presence), based on census indicators over three periods (2000–2020). The analysis did not provide conclusive evidence that the EZLN's presence significantly boosted aggregate development indicators in the municipality studied, although there are important variations in specific variables such as female labor force participation or access to basic goods.

From a political perspective, this suggests that autonomy models like Zapatismo may have differentiated effects, more visible at the community or qualitative level than in aggregate data. This poses methodological and epistemological challenges in the evaluation of alternative development models.

The work provides a territorial and critical reading of development, opening the door to analyses that combine quantitative data with community approaches. It highlights the importance of developing more appropriate measurement instruments to evaluate unconventional development experiences.

Future studies could expand the sample to more Zapatista and non-Zapatista municipalities, include qualitative interviews with community actors, and evaluate specific dimensions such as educational attainment, access to healthcare, and food security. It is also crucial to design new indicators that reflect the priorities of Indigenous peoples themselves, overcoming the limitations of conventional censuses.

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